

Analytical Applications of Schiff Base Nickel Complexes in the Gravimetric Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba

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MIxed metal complexes of Schiff bases of 3 Formyl Salicylic acid (3FSA) and ethylene diamine (en), 1, 2 diaminopropane (DAP) or 1, 2 diamino 2-methyl propane (DAMP) have also been isolated as solids and thoroughly studied¹. Analytical applications of Schiff base copper complexes in the gravimetric estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba also have been discussed by Rawat in an earlier communication².

The series of complexes contain a co-ordinated nickel ion in inner position associated with a second metal ion which could be an alkali metal or an alkaline earth metal. A few metal complexes of Schiff bases of 3 FSA with en were first reported by Poddar³. During the course of investigation it was observed that elements like Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba can be quantitatively precipitated by the [enLNiNa₂], [DAPLNiNa₂] or [DAMPLNiNa₂] complex as [enLNiX], [DAPLNiX], and [DAMPLNiX] where X=Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba. In the present communication the analytical use of Schiff base nickel complexes for the gravimetric determination of Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba has been described.

Colour of the complexes ranges from red to yellow, decompose above 250° and are diamagnetic.

	C	H	N	Ni	Na
[en L Ni] Na ₂ , calcd.	47.31	2.64	6.12	12.84	10.06
C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₆ N ₂ NiNa ₂ found	47.01	2.59	6.10	12.81	10.00
[DAPL Ni] Na ₂ calcd.	48.46	2.99	5.94	12.46	9.76
C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂ NiNa ₂ found	48.31	2.95	5.91	12.39	9.80
[DAMPL Ni] Na ₂ calcd.	49.52	3.31	5.77	12.10	9.48
C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂ Ni Na ₂ found	50.00	3.40	5.78	12.13	9.51

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. quality. 3 FSA was prepared from salicylic acid and hexamine by the method of Duff and Bills⁴ and this was allowed to react in alcoholic solution with half the gram mol of en, DAP or DAMP to prepare the Schiff base as suggested by Poddar³. The water soluble complexes of [en L Ni]Na₂, [DAPL Ni]Na₂ and [DAMPL Ni]Na₂ are the basic compounds which were used as analytical reagents. The Na₂Ni complex of the Schiff base was obtained by mixing alcoholic solution of A. R. nickel acetate to the caustic soda solution of the Schiff base. The beautiful orange colour complex obtained was quite stable in the air. It was washed with small quantity of alcohol on the gooch crucible and dried in vacuo for sometime and later heated to 120° in an oven. The complexes were hydrated to different degrees but heating them first in vacuo for about 2 hr. and then for about 2 hr. in an oven at 120° gave water free complexes. The dry complexes were used for the quantitative estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba at about a pH of 5 to 7. The highly acidic solution led to the formation of H₂Ni complexes.

Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba : 0.001 M aqueous solution of Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba salts were prepared. 50 ml of this solution was taken and diluted to 200 ml and to this 100 ml of 0.001 M Na₂Ni complex solution was added. Immediate precipitation takes place. The precipitate was kept for digestion on steam bath for half an hour. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered glass crucible, washed three times with water and finally three times with alcohol. Mg Ni complex being soluble in alcohol was washed with ether. Finally the precipitate was dried in an oven at 100° for about 2 hr. The precipitate so obtained has the composition [en L Ni X], [DAPL Ni X] and [DAMPL Ni X] where X is Mg, Ca, Sr, or Ba. The results are recorded in Table 1 and composition of complexes will be reported elsewhere.

Analysis of the complex : The analysis of the metal ion Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba in the complex was carried out by standard methods. Nickel was determined gravimetrically as dimethyl glyoxime complex after destroying the ligand by sulphuric acid and nitric acid treatment. Magnesium was determined gravimetrically as Mg ammonium phosphate in the solution after removal of nickel. Calcium was determined using a flame photometer.

TABLE-1 (ALL WEIGHTS REPORTED HERE ARE IN MG)

Sl. No.	Estimation of X as [Y L Ni X]	Metal X taken	Y=en			Y=DAP			Y=DAMP		
			Weight of complex	X found	Error	Weight of complex	X found	Error	Weight complex	X found	Error
1.	Mg as	30	539.0	30.1	+0.10	553.2	29.92	-0.08	573.3	30.08	+0.08
	[Y L Ni Mg]	40	727.1	40.06	+0.06	739.6	40.00	0.00	760.5	39.90	-0.10
		50	895.8	50.02	+0.02	924.7	50.01	+0.01	954.9	50.10	+0.10
2.	Ca as	30	338.5	30.06	+0.06	347.6	29.94	-0.06	359.4	30.05	+0.05
	[Y L Ni Ca]	40	450.5	40.01	+0.01	463.4	39.91	-0.09	479.6	40.10	+0.10
		50	562.4	49.95	-0.05	580.73	50.02	+0.02	598.9	50.08	+0.08
3.	Sr as	30	171.2	30.08	+0.08	176.1	30.09	+0.09	180.5	30.02	+0.02
	[Y L Ni Sr]	40	227.6	39.99	-0.01	234.7	40.10	+0.10	240.1	40.05	+0.05
		50	284.3	49.96	-0.04	292.6	50.00	0.00	300.8	50.03	+0.03
4.	Ba as	30	120.5	29.90	-0.10	122.1	29.93	-0.07	126.0	30.00	0.00
	[Y L Ni Ba]	40	159.4	39.89	-0.11	163.5	39.90	-0.10	167.7	39.94	-0.06
		50	199.4	49.91	-0.09	204.6	49.95	-0.05	210.0	50.01	+0.01

Results and Discussion

Analytical data in Table 1 show that the metal complex i.e. Na_2Ni complexes can be used for the gravimetric estimation of magnesium, calcium, strontium and barium. Solutions containing as little as 10 mg can be determined by this method. Common anions like chloride, bromide, nitrate etc. do not interfere in the determination of the coloured complexes [YL Ni Mg], [Y L Ni Ca], [Y L Ni Sr] and [Y L Ni Ba]. The complexes are stable upto 250° , above this temperature they start decomposing. Only the MgNi complexes are soluble in methyl alcohol. The remaining are insoluble in water, acetone, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, benzene and pyridine.

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H_2O_2 -Extinction Coefficients of Homoionic Soils (Na-, K-, NH_4 - and H-soils) in Aqueous Media at Different Temperatures

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THE study of H_2O_2 decomposition by different homoionic soils (particularly of U. P., India) appears to have not been done, although works are available to show the effect of different salts, pH, organic

fertilizers and mild acids on soil catalase activity¹. Here, attempts have been made to show the extent of H_2O_2 decomposition by a few samples of U. P. soils saturated with Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ and H^+ ions.

Eleven U. P. soils (0-6") belonging to different soil-climatic regions were collected and H_2O_2 -extinction coefficients (K) of their monovalent homoionic forms (Na-, K-, NH_4 - and H-soils) were determined in aqueous media at 20° , 30° and 40° .

To make these soil samples homoionic with respect to H-, Na-, NH_4 -, and K-ions, they were treated with N-HCl, N-NaCl, N- NH_4Cl and N-KCl solutions (1 : 10) respectively and shaken well. After 24 hr, the soil suspensions were filtered through Buchner funnel and leached four times with the same solutions. Finally, the samples left on the filter paper were then removed, dried, powdered and passed through 100-mesh sieve, for subsequent work.

For the estimation of H_2O_2 decomposition, 2.0 g. of each soil sample was taken in 100 ml. measuring flask and volume was made up with 0.1 N H_2O_2 solution. The flasks were then kept in a thermostat at 20° , 30° and 40° . From each flask, 20.0 ml. aliquots were taken out after 5, 15, 30 and 60 min. and were centrifuged to get a clear solution and from this solution H_2O_2 decomposition was estimated iodometrically². A blank experiment was also carried out. K value was calculated from the first order equation of kinetics as follows :

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where, K = H_2O_2 - extinction coefficients, a = initial concentration of H_2O_2 , x = quantity of H_2O_2 decomposed, and t = time of reaction.

A perusal of Table 1 would clearly show that the K values recorded at 5, 15, 30 and 60 mts. did not give constant values and, therefore, did not obey first order reaction equation. This was expected because of the heterogenous nature of soil. Pure H_2O_2 solution in pure catalase will, however, follow first order equation